

EFFECTS OF FEMINISM ON GENDER EQUALITY**Dr. Reni Francis***I/c Principal***Ms. Anaam Khan and Ms. Tamanna Midday***Student teacher**MES's Pillai College of Education and Research, Chembur***Abstract**

“A Feminist is anyone who recognizes the equality and full of humanity of women and men”

Feminism has been a part of our life since the 18th century, either directly or indirectly. Women have always faced issues of inequality and dominance for a very long time. And this inequality and injustice led to Feminist movements. We had the first wave of feminism during the 18th century after which we had the second and the third waves. We are currently witnessing the fourth wave. Each wave had different issues which were tackled. But in the modern days feminism has gotten a bad name, which can attributed because of various reasons such as the unawareness of the term feminism and what it actually stands for. In our research paper we have looked into the idea that whether people are aware about the term feminism in its correct definition or there is a different idea and what can be done to promote feminism in a positive way.

Introduction

Almost all of the world has been burdened because of patriarchy, it is the main reason why women all across the world have faced inequalities and injustice. This led to the movement of feminism. Feminism is a range of social movements, political movements and ideologies that aim to define, establish and achieve political, economic personal and social equality of the sexes. It incorporates the position that societies prioritize the male point of view and that women are treated unfairly within those societies. Efforts to change that include fighting gender stereotypes and seeking to establish educational and professional opportunities for women that are equal to those for men.

Theoretical background

The feminist history is split into three waves each with slightly different aims based on prior progress. But at the core of it, it has always asked for equal rights for both the sexes. The first wave of feminism which started initially in the 18th century and became full-fledged from 19th century onwards, tackled issues like legal inequalities which included voting rights. The second wave started in the 1960s to 1980s. After World War II, the second wave of feminism focused on the workplace, sexuality, family and reproductive rights. This time is often dismissed as offensive, outdated and obsessed with middle class white women's problem which is a misconception, on the contrary many women during the second wave were initially part of the Black Civil Rights movement, Anti-Vietnam Movement, Chicano Rights Movement, Asian - American Civil Rights Movement, Gay and Lesbian Movement and many other groups fighting for equality. Many of the women supporters of the aforementioned groups felt their voices are not being heard and felt that in order to gain respect in co-ed organizations they first needed to address gender equality concerns. Women cared so much about these civil issues that they wanted to strengthen their voices by first fighting for gender equality to ensure they would be heard. Unlike the former movements, the term 'feminist' becomes less critically received by the female population due to the varying feminist outlooks. There are the ego-cultural feminists, the radicals, the liberal/reforms, the electoral, academic, ecofeminism and many more.

The main issues were prefaced by the work done by the previous waves of women. The fight continued to vanquish the disparities in male and female pay and the reproductive rights of women. This wave was about acceptance and a true understanding of the term 'feminism'. While the conditions have improved abroad, a huge population of women in India still suffer due to the patriarchal system that exist in our society. In the Indian

context feminism has a long way to go to achieve equality between both the sexes. It should be noted that tremendous progress has been made since the first wave, but there is still much to be done. Due to the range of feminist issues today, it is much harder to put a label on what a feminist looks like- leading to a brand new generation rallying for equality and women's rights.

Methodology

The data was collected from 40 people through a survey. The data was analyzed both qualitatively and quantitatively using coding method. The questions were:

1. Are you aware of the term feminism?
2. What is feminism according to you?
3. How many waves of feminism are you aware of?
4. When was the first wave of feminism started?
5. Do you think modern feminism has given a bad name to feminism?
6. Do you think Feminist movements like #metoo have helped in women empowerment?
7. Are you in favor of feminism?
8. Does India need feminism?
9. Do you think feminism has played a huge role in promoting gender equality?
10. How will you promote feminism so that it is seen in a positive light?

Research findings

Question 1: Are you aware of the term feminism?

76.67% were aware of the term feminism, 23.3% said that they have a slight idea of the term.

Question 2: What is feminism according to you?

Question 3: How many waves of feminism are you aware of?

26.67% said they were only aware of one wave, 20% said there were 2, 40% said there were 3 and 13% said there are 4 waves of feminism.

Question 4: When was the first wave of feminism started?

82.26% said it was from the 18th century to 20th century, 10.37% said 15th century to 16th century, 7% 13th century to 17th century

Question 5: Do you think modern feminism has given a bad name to feminism?

70% agreed to this and 30% said no to this.

Question 6: Do you think feminist movements like #metoo have helped in women empowerment?

13.33% strongly agree to this, 66.67% agree to this, 13.33% disagree to this and 6.67% strongly disagree to this.

Question 7: Are you in favor of feminism?

65% are in favor, while 35% are not in favor

Question 8: Does India need feminism?

40% strongly agree, 45% agree and 15% disagree to this.

Question 9: Do you think feminism has played a huge role in promoting gender equality?

80% say yes to this, 10% say no, 10% are unsure.

Question 10: How will you promote feminism so that it is seen in a positive light?**Conclusion**

Feminism talks about equal rights for both the sexes. However we find that modern feminism has been portrayed in such a way that feminism has now become a negative word. This is mainly due unawareness and misconceptions.

Our research has found that people are not completely aware of the term feminism in its correct form. They are either unaware or misinformed. People are also unaware about the history of feminist movements which is important to know to actually understand how it has impacted women empowerment. Only when there is awareness and when the misconceptions are clarified, only then one can truly promote feminism in a positive light.

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